

Institutional Factors Influencing Access to County Vocational Education and Training Institutions in Makueni County, Kenya

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study was to investigate the influence of institutional factors on access to County Vocational Education and Training institutions in Makueni County, Kenya. The study was informed by the existence of a large number of youths in the County who have not enrolled in CVETIs hence leading to high population of idle youths with low or no relevant employable skills which contributes to increased dependency ratio, high unemployment rates, engagement in drug and substance abuse and other social-evils. The study sought to investigate whether, the career guidance services influence access to County Vocational Education and Training Institutions in Makueni County, Kenya. The study was guided by Human Capital Theory (HCT). The study employed descriptive research design. The study targeted 28 registered Public Vocational institutions in Makueni County. The study used stratified simple random sampling and purposive sampling techniques to obtain a random sample of 21 managers, 87 instructors and 316 trainees drawn from 21 randomly selected Vocational institutions. Questionnaires, interview schedule and an observation check list were used to collect data. Data were processed and analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively. Descriptive statistics that is, frequency distributions, percentages, means and standard deviations were generated and used in describing and discussing the research findings. Statistical tests were done using a T-test and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 95% Confidence Interval of the difference ($\alpha=0.05$). An independent sample t-test was conducted to compare mean difference between if career guidance influence access to county vocational education as well as training institutions and professional qualification of the managers. The findings of the study revealed that, Most of the vocational institutions have no organized and functional career guidance departments to provide in-depth information on individual courses, inadequate career guidance services has an influence on access to CVETIs and trainees' career progression. Based on this findings the study recommended that the institutions should establish functional career guidance departments to provide in-depth information on individual courses and career guidance on vocational education to be introduced at the lower level of basic education.

KEY WORDS: Access, County Vocational Education and Training Institutions, Institutional Factors, Prospective Trainees.

INTRODUCTION

The process of career decision making is a complex and an involving moment in one's life especially for the adolescent. It is a critical decision that basic education graduates need to make at the end of their compulsory basic education to decide between an academic or Vocational Education and Training (VET) pathway. To make an informed decision on career choice, the student should be carefully guided with the changing nature of jobs and work place requirements in mind. Making an insight career decision is an important undertaking that creates an opportunity to acquire quality and relevant skills, knowledge and other attributes that enables a graduate to participate competitively in the knowledge economy and remain competitive in the 21st century labour market (Carnevale, Smith, & Strohl, 2013).

A well thought education and training pathway based on the student's abilities and interest has a significant impact on one's career success, career progression, job satisfaction and efficient service delivery (Farid, 2019). "Quality and affordable Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) is one of the United Nations Sustainable Development agenda items for ensuring equal access to education and training for all by the year 2030 (United Nations, 2015)." This implies that the youthful population across the world should acquire quality and relevant employable skills, for employment in both formal and informal sectors, create job opportunities for others and promote entrepreneurial culture. In this regard, an all-inclusive education and training is a right. Every person regardless of gender, age, religion, disability or ethnic background has an equal opportunity to education and training as

outlined by various Sustainable Development objectives (United Nations, 2015). Nevertheless, as the fundamental right to accessing education and training is being recognized within educational reforms frameworks across the world, young people and adults still face difficulties in accessing TVET programmes largely associated with discriminatory career guidance practices. (Garcia, Toledo, & Rodriguez, 2020). The significant recognition of the importance of TVET in international discourse and policies is yet to shape up the image of TVET when compared with the academic education track. The challenge is experienced more in the third world countries where it has been observed that the enrolment in TVET has not improved significantly many basic education graduates continue to prefer the academic education track as their first choice. This has made TVET to have a low image and therefore making it a universal concern (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2018). Due to negative public image of VET, enrollment in TVET is major concern for educational stakeholders and the education sector at large. According to Farid (2019), some institutional related factors have a direct contribution to the low enrolment witnessed in VET. Some of these factors include inadequate VET instructors with inadequate industrial experience, insufficient training facilities and skewed career guidance programs to learners while at the basic education level of schooling.

Globally, TVET has significantly influenced the development of knowledge, skills, competencies and expertise necessary for development initiatives which are critical for sustainable societies and economies. To this end, the quality of skill development process determines the quality of the generated of human capital in terms of knowledge, skills and appropriate attitudes (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2020). Basically, the acquisition and effective application of these attributes results to sustainable economic development, enhances social mobility, national cohesion and development. The skills and knowledge that youthful population acquire must therefore be relevant to the current economy, meet their needs and aspirations. Consequently, it is important to ensure that, this training sub-sector undergoes continuous technological development to cope with current global trends, enhance equity in access and develop resilient training courses so as to equip the fast growing youth population with modern industrial skills for economic and social progress (Otero, 2019). Career guidance in China is a primary means for effective integration of youth population in the world of work through guided career paths that enables them to pursue vocational education. The China policy framework, “Modern Vocational Education System Construction Plan (2014-2020),” creates opportunities for lifelong learning making vocational training more attractive which enhances career progression with open pathways for higher education and training. This has contributed to the production of quality TVET graduates whose capacities make them more competitive locally and internationally to promote the county’s productivity which has led to increase in her real income and improved standards of living (People's Republic of China, 2018).

The socio-economic advancement of Taiwan, Singapore, and Hong Kong, is attributed to the strategic mechanisms of linking the world of skill development and the world of work. Basically, Singapore’s TVET sector offers career-oriented education and training focusing on remaining relevant and responsive to industrial manpower demand which promotes public perception on importance and value of TVET. The Government of Singapore has highly invested in TVET to provide quality education and training which address the training needs of her population and ensuring that by ensuring that the acquired skills remain relevant to the job market (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2020). Its significant achievement in skills development has been necessitated by the equal participation of both the academia and the industry. The skills development is driven by various TVET strategies and policy documents which includes; Skills-future Singapore Agency Act 2016 (No 24 of 2016), Workforce Singapore Agency Act 2003, Industry Transformation Maps 2016. (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2020). Education in Kenya is anchored on the Constitution of Kenya as a fundamental human right. This has informed policy provisions developed to address the constitutional requirements and direct national aspirations (Republic of Kenya, 2012). National aspirations and the critical role of education are articulated in the Kenya Vision 2030 which advocates for the link between training institutions and the job market in order to create stock of human capital with relevant skills, competencies, soft skills and attitudes essential in the work place (Republic of Kenya, 2014). TVET, in Kenya education system largely includes trade tests vocational centres; artisan, craft and diploma courses in TTIs as well as craft and diploma courses in national polytechnics, leading to trade tests, certificates and diplomas in various disciplines.

The prospective trainees for TVET includes youths who drop out of the basic education system either at primary or secondary school levels, primary level graduate who fail to enroll at secondary school level and secondary level graduates who perform below the university admission requirements. The Government has provided policy direction for education reforms to address prevailing training gaps in TVET sub-sector which encourages a strong public and private sector partnerships. The Kenya Vision 2030

underscores the critical role played by TVET in generation of human and social capital necessary for sustainable social, political and economic development (Republic of Kenya, 2012). Makueni County recognizes access to VET as an important avenue for creation of a well trained workforce for the County's sustainable social economic transformation. Makueni County has rebranded the village youth polytechnics to County Vocational Education and Training Institutions (CVETIs) in an attempt to upgrade them in light of the advent of technology and align the VET with the needs of the job market (County Government of Makueni, 2016). Most of the youths in the County have not enrolled in CVETIs denying them to acquire employable skills. VET remains paramount to enable one make a step from being unemployable to employability. Most of them are idle. This has increased dependency on working population, led to high cases of unemployment, engagement in drugs and substance abuse and other social-evils. They are vulnerable and poorest in a total population of (26%). The youths are left with no option but to destroy their environment to survive. Access to CVETIs remains an issue of concern in Makueni County (County Government of Makueni, 2016).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

As the fundamental right to accessing education and training is being recognized within educational reforms frameworks across the world, young people and adults still face difficulties in accessing TVET institutions. The significant recognition of the importance of TVET in international discourse and policies is yet to shape up the image of TVET as prospective trainees continue to prefer the academic education track as their first choice regardless of their inability to meet the minimum entry requirements. The challenge is experienced more by the third world countries whose investment in TVET sub-sector is significantly low. This has led TVET to have a low image, unattractive and therefore making it a universal concern. Currently, in Kenya there is a high percentage of youth population who are legible for training in Vocational institutions as a result of mass Basic Secondary education graduates whose performance is below the university entry requirements and other tertiary institutions. The Government's efforts to devolve VET to Counties to enhance skills development, employment of affirmative action to increase enrolment of the high number of prospective trainees has not to a large extent increased access to CVET institutions whose enrolment has remained low both nationally and in Makueni County. The low enrolment is worrying prompting a question, what could be the cause to low enrolment? The idle unemployable youthful population increased dependency on the working population, led to high unemployment cases, engagement in drugs and substance abuse and other social-evils which is a major development challenge. These makes the youth more vulnerable hence they are left with no option but to destroy their environment to survive causing a continued environmental degradation. Little empirical evidence exists on whether institutional factors influence enrolment in CVETIs especially in Makueni County. In view of this gap, this study investigated the contribution of institutional factors on access to CVET institutions so as to re-strengthen the practical skills, knowledge, and improve the enrolment in County Vocational Education and Training institutions. TVET remains the first paramount step from being unemployable to employability.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study was to investigate the influence of institutional factors on access to County Vocational Education and Training institutions in Makueni County.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The study was guided by the following specific objective.

To investigate the extent to which career guidance influence access to County Vocational Education and Training institutions in Makueni County, Kenya

NULL HYPOTHESES

In order to test the independent variables, a null hypotheses was developed.

H_03 . There is no significant relationship between career guidance and access to Vocational Education and Training institutions in Makueni County, Kenya

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study was guided by Human Capital Theory (HCT) whose origin can be traced to the work of Adam Smith in 1976. The theory affirms that, the sustainable social-economic and resilient well-being of a community is a function of its financial capital, quality

labour force, natural resources endowment as well as knowledge and skills of its population. This theory holds that, when knowledge and skills of the population increase, will yield to improved social-economic outcomes for both individuals and societies. Skill development is therefore viewed as the core means of improving ones productivity, efficiency, economic outcomes, well-being of the society and other lifetime direct and in direct benefits (Crocker, 2006).

HCT affirms that investment in skills development is expensive and involving, making it necessary to project human resource needs and requirements of the labour market, training needs analysis and establishment of training gaps. Since early 1960s, the theory has been influential in the Western education planning and informing framework of Government policies. This study focuses on the skill development processes and the training environment required to achieve the desired education and training outcomes. The theory fits in this study based on the evidence that, education and training is an investment whose relevance can be guaranteed in labour market driven institutions (Psachoropoulos & Woodhall, 1997). Using the theory, the study sought to investigate whether institutional factors have an influence on trainees' access to CVETIs in Makueni County Kenya.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Career guidance and trainees' access to CVET institutions

Career guidance services has been defined by Watts and Fretwell in a World Bank report (2004), as consultative services aimed at helping people to make informed decisions on career choices, education and training decisions and occupational mobility choices despite their age and to manage their careers (Watts & Fretwell, 2004). The concept of vocational guidance can be traced from the contribution parsons 1909 who worked with young people to help them make decisions concerning their vocations. Consequently, he is considered the father of vocational guidance. On his opinion he argued that the young face a lot of internal and external pressure in the process of their career decision making. He adds that, for them to make the right career choice they need to be assisted to reach a wise choice. This can be done considering self-assessment to oneself, one's aptitudes, abilities, interests, ambitions, required recourses and vocational training options available (Parsons, 1909). For this to happen, a well-thought career requires a professional and a well-developed career guidance system that is able to address training needs of the student (Farid, 2019).

Career information basically includes information on training courses offered by various training institutions in the economy, related occupations, minimum admission requirements, cost of training and the financing options available, career paths for future career progression and labour market information which enables an individual to make a decision to enroll and pursue an area of interest based on the set enrolment requirement (Farid, 2019). Enrolment for education and training is proportionately influenced by the career education passed to the population formally or informally which makes individuals to make informed decisions on their career choice and managing their career development. Career guidance enable the young population and others to make a choice in wide range of available training opportunities and training courses, based on their distinctive abilities, interests and ability to both direct and in direct costs of training. This implies that, career guidance is one of the key tools which is indispensable within TVET sub-sector. Enrolment to a TVET institution is a clear indication that an individual has made a deliberate choice on a career pathway to shape his/her skill development ambitions (UNESCO, 2013). Farid (2019), citing Hogg (1999), pointed out that, through career development sessions, the young population find information about the available training opportunities. During this critical moment, the adolescent need the guidance from experienced career counselors and others who have experience in career decision-making process (Farid, 2019). Based on this argument, access to (VET) largely depends on information on the availability of training opportunities and programmes passed through career awareness. It is further noted that, training institutions in many developing countries traditionally have not seen transition to vocational training as a significant concern of their human resource development and their mission too leading to low development of careers advice which has influenced enrolment (UNESCO, 2013).

A study conducted by UNESCO-UNEVOC between 2019 -2020 in ten countries (Australia, Chile, Costa Rica, German, Ghana, Jamaica, Lebanon, the Netherland, the Philippines and South Africa on boosting gender equality in science and technology, a challenge for TVET programmes and career indicates that, educational career advice provided by educational staff and career advisers has a strong influence on prospective trainees' choice for TVET training programme (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2020). This means that the shared information influence the image of TVET which affects the personal choices on the areas of education and training for career development. This to a large extent influence the enrolments in various education and training institutions leading to low enrolment if the image created on TVET is negative. A study by Watters (2009), on "making initial VET more attractive for

prospective trainees” observed that, careers departments have inadequate expertise to guide the trainees on career progression making it difficult to enroll for higher level training courses in the institution or in other related institutions. Further, to increase the capacity to make deliberate choice for vocational education and training she states that, career expertise should provide exhaustive career advice necessary for the prospective trainees to decide appropriately the kind of course to enroll for in a collage (Watters E. , 2009). This indicated that, inadequate career guidance arrangements, limited information on career progression and labour market remunerations leads to low drive for career progression in TVET leading to low enrolment rates in TVET institutions.

A case study done in four Higher Education institutions in Ireland by Eleanor (2015), to examine the students’ experiences of the transition to higher education in Ireland, which focused on the extent to which the skills, competences and orientations help students to succeed in their choices for enrollment and participation in Higher Education institutions indicated that, the prominent factors influencing access to Higher Education is inadequate accurate initial information on the course requirements, components and the standards of a training programmes, unrealistic expectations in ones future career and lack of gradual preparation to enroll in TVET at the early stages of schooling (Eleanor, 2015). Based on this insight, development of a framework to support students at their early stages of schooling (basic education level) to understand the basic expectations and requirements for various career pathways is considered critical to inform their career choice decisions. The study suggested for an introduction of guidance programme that touches on realities of studying different courses and the collage life in general at the secondary school level to boost access to higher education. A study done by Andiema & Manasi (2021), on female students’ participation in TVET in West Pokot County found out that, most of the girls who could not enroll for secondary and tertiary education after sitting for their KCPE, in various years, were not aware of the training opportunities available in VTCs in the County (Andiema & Manasi, 2021). This findings brings out an information gap in the society about the existing training opportunities in VTCs for boys and girls to acquire competitive skills and knowledge for gainful employment.

A study by Farid (2019), on the factors that influence prospective trainees’ decision to enroll for Vocational Education and Training in Tajikistan established that youths face more challenges in the process of making informed career decisions in those Countries where career guidance systems are poor or does not exist all together. The study indicated that, the youths who live in the rural areas where there is less opportunities for industrial information that could enhance their career awareness as the most affected. The absence of such information noted to limit them from developing interests and aptitudes for the careers and training opportunities available for skill development in the fast changing knowledge economy (Farid, 2019). Basic education graduates (secondary school level graduates) all along their schooling time long to join universities for degrees programmes whose entry requirements may be a challenge to meet. They then encounter a dilemma about making a choice on their career path way when faced with Vocational training, informal sector and middle level colleges as the only option available. According to Safarmamad (2019), secondary school graduates in Tajikistan, encounter challenges in their process to decide the postsecondary institutions they would enroll to pursue their education and training. To assess the influence of career guidance on access to TVET, this study sought to establish whether, career guidance information determines one’s decision to enroll in public VTCs in Makueni County which is an ASAL region in Kenya.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design

Research design has been defined as the guiding plan that is used to answer a research question (Orodho, Khatete, & Mugiraneza, 2016). From this definition, a research design outlines the specific methods and procedures to be followed in the data collection exercise, how the collected data will be analyzed and presented for a meaningful interpretation and generalization. It’s also described as the conceptual structure that guides a scientific study whose procedure involves collecting, measuring, organizing and analyzing a data set (Kothari & Gaurav, 2014). The selection of an appropriate research design determines the quality of data to be collected. This makes the research design selection the most important step in the research process (Kothari & Gaurav, 2014). In this study, descriptive research design was used. The use of this design enabled the researcher to obtain needed information by interviewing, administering a questionnaire to the sampled subjects and making observations. Using this design the researcher summarized the collected data in a way that provided the desired descriptive information to respond to questions by analyzing without manipulating the independent variables relating to institutional factors influencing trainees’ access to CVET institutions in Makueni County.

Target population

Target population is the whole group of subjects from which a representative sample might be drawn. It consists of all the elements or items whose characteristics are being studied (Orodho, Khatete, & Mugiraneza, 2016). Population consists of the universe representing the elements whose characteristics are of great concern to the researcher and from which a representative sample is drawn and hence generalization of the research findings. The study targeted the 28 registered public County Vocational Education and Training institutions in Makueni County. The population comprised of 28 managers, 99 instructors and 3609 trainees. The target population was 3736.

Sample size and sampling procedure

The study used stratified simple random sampling to obtain a representative sample since the target population comprised of three groups of informants. Using this technique, the population was stratified into three strata of the managers, instructors and trainees which were non-overlapping. Using simple random technique the subjects were selected from each stratum whose effect was to improve representativeness and reduce the sampling error. (Orodho, Khatete, & Mugiraneza, 2016). The sample size of the informants was determined by use of Taro Yamani formula at 0.05 level of significance with a confidence coefficient of 95% as shown (Yamane, 1967). 21 managers, 87 instructors and 316 trainees were sampled representing 75%, 56.5% and 9.5 % respectively.

Data collection instruments

The researcher used interview schedule, observation check lists and questionnaires as the data collection instruments for this study. The researcher interviewed 12 managers who were purposively sampled and had been identified from document analysis at the County youth skill development and ICT offices. An observation schedule was used to enable the researcher to verify the information already collected from the informants. Three sets of questionnaires were constructed by the researcher to collect desired information from County Vocational Education and Training institutions managers, instructors and trainees.

Data collection procedure

The researcher was granted an approval by the University of Nairobi that issued a letter of full registration that enabled the researcher to approach the appropriate agencies in the country to seek permission to collect data. With this approval, the researcher first applied for a research license from National Commission for Science, Technology and Innovation (NACOSTI). The researcher was licensed to conduct research in Makueni County for a period of one year from the date of license issuance (license No. NACOSTI/P/19/1152) as shown in appendix VII. Clearance from the County Commissioner in Makueni County was done on 19th September 2019 who issued a research authorization letter and on the said date an approval by the Chief Education Officer and ICT made. The document is attached as in appendix VIII.

Data analysis techniques

The researcher cleaned the raw data, coded the data, entered and then analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) IBM version 23. Descriptive statistics were generated and used in describing and discussing the research findings without manipulating the respondents' opinion. The standard deviation was used to measure how the responses align with the mean and describe the degree of consistency within the responses. A statistical analysis for managers output – independent sample T-test for independent variables was done. The T-test was considered to be the most appropriate for this study since the standard deviation was unknown and the sample size for the managers was less than 30 ($n < 30$). This was based on Orodho et.al (2016) who states that, when the population standard deviation is unknown and the sample size is less than 30, the t-test is the most appropriate. A statistical analysis for instructors and trainees output whose sample was greater than 30 ($n > 30$) was done using the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) as the preferred test on mean between two or more variables for association. The ANOVA was used to test for significant difference between mean of three or more variables between groups and within groups' variations. It enabled the researcher to determine whether the given classification is important in affecting the results and to test the null hypothesis that the means of three groups of variables are the same against the alternative hypothesis that not all means are the same, at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance to test the null hypothesis (Orodho, Khatete, & Mugiraneza, 2016). Quantitative data from interview and open ended items in the questionnaire were organized according to themes, coded and integrated with data from closed ended questions for frequencies and percentages. The analyzed data was presented through tabular representation of descriptive statistics tables for each variable.

Research Findings and Discussions

Objective 3 - To evaluate the extent to which career guidance influenced access to CVETIs in Makueni County, Kenya This objective looked at the contribution of in-depth information on the realities of various courses offered by vocational education and training institutions and the extent to which this information influenced access to CVETIs. This was based on the assumption that the trainees could have unrealistic expectations on their future career, the realities of studying a certain vocation and trainees diversity background preparation on higher education which may have influenced their transition to vocational education and training. The influence of career guidance was explored to establish the extent to which career guidance influence access to vocational education and training institutions. A questionnaire item was constructed to establish the source of information that informed the trainees’ choice to join the vocational education and training institution. This item was administered to trainees only. The researcher posted a question to establish how the trainees first learned about VET. The responses were recorded in Table 4.36.

Table 4.36 How the trainees first learned about CVETIs training courses

Statement	frequency	percent (%)
Through teachers in their previous school	31	9.9
Through family members	45	14.4
Through peers	152	48.7
Through the media	36	11.5
Through self-discovery	48	15.4
	312	100.0

Table 4.36 shows that, 48.7 % of trainees learned about CVETIs through their peers. Such a revelations is a clear indication that there is a limited concern on career guidance at the lower levels of schooling where the role played by teachers to inform the students about vocational training was rated at 9.9%. A study conducted by UNESCO-UNEVOC between 2019 -2020 in ten countries “(Australia, Chile, Costa Rica, German, Ghana, Jamaica, Lebanon, the Netherland, the Philippines and South Africa on boosting gender equality in science and technology, a challenge for TVET programmes and career,” placed a teacher at a critical point in a student’s career choice.

The study indicates that, “Educational career advice provided by educational staff such as teachers and career advisers has a strong influence on the choices of students to education and training courses” (UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2020). This findings were supported by Farid (2019), citing Hogg (1999), when he pointed out that, through career development sessions, the young population find information about the available training opportunities. During this critical moment, the adolescent need the guidance from experienced career counselors and others who have experience in career decision-making process (Farid, 2019). Based on this argument, access to (VET) largely depends on information on the availability of training opportunities and programmes passed through career awareness. It is further noted that, training institutions in many developing countries traditionally have not seen transition to vocational training as a significant concern of their human resource development and their mission too leading to low development of careers advice which has influenced enrolment to vocational training (UNESCO, 2013). To establish whether the CVETIs carry out career guidance programmes within the institution to enhance career progression which is an ingredient for increased enrolment, six questionnaire items were constructed and presented to managers, instructors and trainees. The questionnaire yielded responses as reported in Table 4.37

Respondent	Yes		No			
	Frequency %	valid percent	frequency %	valid percent		
Managers	10	47.6	47.6	11	52.4	52.4
Instructors	42	48.3	48.3	45	51.7	51.7
Trainees	116	37.2	37.2	196	62.8	62.8

Table 4.37 shows the analyzed data for managers, instructors and trainees on the provision of career guidance services within the vocational institutions. The three categories of informants indicate that, institutions does not offers such services. This implies that the trainees are denied the opportunity to explore the expectations surrounding the details of their career paths. The provision of in-depth information on the realities of a particular course could encourage the trainees to progressively enroll for higher levels of training which could improve the social acceptance of VET. An item on whether career guidance influenced access to CVETIs was presented to the three categories of respondents. The questionnaire yielded the data in Table 4.38

Table 4.38 Responses on the influence of career guidance on access to CVETIs

Respondent	YES			NO		
	Frequency	% valid percent		frequency	% valid percent	
Managers	16	76.2	76.2	5	23.8	23.8
Instructors	69	79.3	79.3	18	20.7	20.7
Trainees	295	94.6	94.6	17	5.4	5.4

Table 4.38 shows that, the responses made by the three categories of informants were rated above 76.0%. This indicates that career guidance influenced access to CVET institutions. The trainees’ response was overwhelming given by 295 out of 312 or 94.6 % of the sampled trainees. The results were in line with the UNESCO report (2013) which indicated “career guidance is an indispensable aspect within TVET.” This argument is based on the premise that “enrolment to a vocational course is an indication that a deliberate career decision has been made”. Other studies have shown that, access to vocational training largely depends on the information about the availability of training opportunities and courses that are offered by a particular training institution that is passed through career awareness (Cathleen, Raffé, Georg, Ammerman, & Watters, 2014). This implies that enrolment for education and training is proportionately influenced by the career education that is gradually passed to the young population formally or informally. Such information makes an individual to make an informed decision on their career based on their diversified intellectual abilities, distinctive interests and the ability to meet both direct and indirect costs of the training. The family has been considered the most influential group in students’ decision-making. It’s through the families that the perception about quality of TVET, family norms and traditions influencing the choice of education track can in communicated (Cathleen, Raffé, Georg, Ammerman, & Watters, 2014).

4.6.1 Responses on existence of career guidance services

To establish whether the Vocational institutions offer career guidance services to the trainees to pass the current industrial needs information and to prepare them for progressive education and training, the researcher posed item to the managers, instructors and the trainees. The questionnaire had an item that required them to rate six statements that were constructed to establish the existence of career guidance services within and out of the Vocational institutions. This was based on a Likert scale of 1 – 5. The responses for managers, instructors and from the trainees were presented in single tables, analyzed and discussed as one whole.

Table 4.39 Managers' responses on availability of career guidance services

Statement	Mean	SDev	SA %	A %	NS %	D %	SD
i). the institution has career guidance department offering career guidance	2.5238	1.07792	4.8	19.0	9.5	57.1	9.5
ii). Trainees are timely encouraged on their career choices	3.6190	1.02353	9.5	66.7	4.8	14.3	4.8
iii). The trainees had prior knowledge on the training courses available in CVETIs	2.1429	1.06234	4.8	9.5	4.8	57.1	23.8

iv). Trainees are guided on career paths for to enhance future career progression	3.0476	1.11697	4.8	43.9	9.5	38.1	4.8
v).inadequate career guidance negatively influence career progression	3.5714	1.12122	9.5	66.7	4.8	9.5	9.5
vi). The instructors provide guidance on the importance of vocational education to enhance further training	2.6667	1.15470	4.8	28.6	4.8	52.4	9.5
Valid N (listwise) N=21							

Key for the mean

Strongly agree	1.0 - 1.7	Agree	1.8 - 2.5	Not sure	2.6 - 3.3
Disagree	3.4 - 4.1	Strongly disagree	4.2 - 5.0		

The descriptive statistics results shown in Table 4.39 reveal that instructors disagree at 57.1 percent that there is career guidance department offering career advice, 19.0 percent of them agreed, those who strongly disagreed not sure were presented at 9.5 percent and those who strongly agreed at 4.8 percent. Item mean rating 2.5238. Standard deviation 1.07792. This implies that majority of the managers feel that there is no career guidance department offering career advice. The descriptive statistics results also indicate that respondents agreed at 66.7 percent that, the institution provides in-depth information on the realities of individual courses, 14.3 percent of them disagreed, while those who strongly agreed at 9.5 percent, and those who strongly disagreed and not sure represented at 4.8 percent. Item mean rating 3.6190. Standard deviation 1.02353. Therefore, descriptive statistics making a conclusion the institution provides in-depth information on the realities of individual courses.

The descriptive analysis results indicate that 57.1 percent of managers disagree that trainee had prior knowledge on training courses offered by CVETIs. Those who strongly agreed were represented by 23.8 percent, 9.5 percent representing those who agreed while 4.8 percent represented strongly agreed and the informants who were not sure. Item mean rating 2.1429. Standard deviation 1.0624. Therefore, most of the informants indicated that the trainee had no prior knowledge on training courses CVETIs. The results indicate that respondents at 42.9 percent of informants agreed that the trainees are informed about career paths available, 38.1 percent disagreed, 9.5 of the informants were not sure, 4.8 percent represented strongly disagreed and those who strongly agreed. Item mean of 3.0476. Standard deviation 1.11697. Majority of managers feel that the trainees are informed about career paths available. The results indicate that informants at 66.7 percent agreed that inadequate career guidance has negatively influenced career progression hence low enrolment, 9.5 percent represented those who strongly disagreed, strongly agreed and disagreed while those not sure represented at 4.8 percent. Item mean rating 3.5714. Standard deviation 1.12122. This indicates that majority of respondents feel inadequate career guidance has negatively influenced career progression hence low enrolment. The descriptive statistics results also indicate that respondents disagree at 52.4 percent that the instructors provide guidance on the importance of vocational education to enhance further training, 28.6 percent agreed, 9.5 percent strongly disagreed and 4.8 percent represented those who were not sure and strongly agreed. Item mean rating 2.6667. Standard deviation 1.15470. Therefore, the descriptive statistics making a conclusion that most of respondents feel that the instructors do not provide guidance on the importance of vocational education to enhance further training.

Table 4.40 Instructors’ responses on availability of career guidance services

Statement	Mean	SDev	SA %	A %	NS %	D %	SD %
i). the institution has career guidance department offering career guidance	2.3678	1.0795	5.7	14.9	3.4	62.1	13.8

ii). Trainees are timely encouraged on their career choices	2.8161	1.12610	3.4	37.9	2.3	49.4	6.9
iii). The trainees had prior knowledge on the training courses available in CVETIs	2.4828	1.27464	6.9	24.1	2.3	43.7	23.0
iv). Trainees are guided on career paths for to enhance future career progression	3.1494	1.1960	3.4	57.5	1.1	26.4	11.5
v).inadequate career guidance negatively influence career progression	3.5402	1.11860	13.8	56.3	5.7	18.4	5.7
vi). The institution campaigns for vocational education through print and other social media	2.8621	1.14295	11.5	21.8	10.3	54.0	2.3

Valid N (listwise) N=87

Key for the mean

Strongly Disagree	1.0 - 1.7	Disagree	1.8 - 2.5	Not sure	2.6 - 3.3
Agree	3.4 - 4.1	Strongly Agree	4.2 - 5.0		

The descriptive statistics results shown in Table 4.40 reveal that instructors disagree at 62.1 percent that there is career guidance department offering career advice, 14.9 percent of them agreed, 13.8 percent strongly disagreed, strongly agreed at 5.7 and not sure at 3.4 percent. Item mean rating 2.3678. Standard deviation of 1.07957 an indication that majority of the respondents feel that there is no career guidance department offering career advice. The descriptive statistics results also indicate that respondents disagree at 49.4 percent that, institution provides in-depth information on the realities of individual courses, 37.9 percent of them agreed, while those who strongly disagreed at 6.9 percent, 3.4 percent strongly agreed and not sure represented at 2.3 percent. Item mean rating 2.8161. Standard deviation 1.12610. Therefore, the descriptive statistics results making a conclusion that the institution does not provide in-depth information on the realities of individual courses.

The descriptive analysis results shown in Table 4.40 indicate that 43.7 percent of instructors disagree that trainee had prior knowledge on training courses CTTI. Those agreed as represented by 24.1 percent, 23.0 percent representing those who strongly disagreed, 6.9 percent strongly agreed while 2.3 percent were not sure. Item mean rating 2.4828. Standard deviation 1.27464. Most of informants indicated that the trainee had no prior knowledge on training courses CVETIs. The results indicate that respondents at 57.5 percent of informants agreed that the trainees are informed about career paths available, 26.4 percent disagreed, 11.5 percent strongly disagreed while those who strongly agreed at 3.4 and not sure represented at 1.1 percent. Item mean rating 3.1494. Standard deviation 1.19620. This implies majority of the respondents feel that the trainees are informed about career paths available.

The results indicate that informants at 56.3 percent agreed that inadequate career guidance has negatively influenced career progression hence low enrolment, 18.4 percent strongly disagreed, strongly agreed at 13.8 percent while those not sure and those strongly disagreed both represented at 5.7 percent. Item mean rating 3.5402. Standard deviation 1.11860. Majority of respondents feel that inadequate career guidance has negatively influenced career progression hence low enrolment. The descriptive statistics results also indicate that respondents disagree at 54.0 percent the instructors provide guidance on the importance of vocational education to enhance further training, 21.8 percent agreed, 11.5 percent strongly agreed, 10.3 percent were not sure while 2.3 percent strongly disagreed. Item mean rating 2.8621. Standard deviation 1.14295. These descriptive statistics implies that, most of the respondents feel that the instructors do not provide guidance on the importance of vocational education to enhance further training. The descriptive statistics analyzed for this item indicates that trainees are not guided by professional career counselors to choose their career paths considering their interest, abilities, weakness, required resources and the existing training opportunities.

Table 4.41 Trainees responses on availability of career guidance services

Statement	Mean	SDev	SA %	A %	NS %	D %	SD
i). the institution has career guidance department offering career guidance	3.0032	1.24621	10.6	38.1	0.0	43.6	7.7
ii). Trainees are timely encouraged on their career choices	3.3141	1.27959	21.2	35.6	0.0	40.1	3.2
iii). The trainees had prior knowledge on the training courses available in CVETIs	2.5090	1.33945	9.9	22.1	1.9	41.0	25.0
iv). Trainees are guided on career paths for to enhance future career progression	3.6474	1.09840	14.7	62.8	1.3	14.7	6.4
v).inadequate career guidance negatively influence career progression	3.7981	0.71789	4.8	81.1	5.1	7.1	1.9
vi). The instructors provide guidance on the importance of vocational education to enhance further training	2.4006	0.89104	2.2	15.4	8.0	68.9	5.4

Valid N =312

Key for the mean

Strongly agree	1.0 - 1.7, Agree	1.8 - 2.5 , Not sure	2.6 - 3.3
Disagree	3.4 - 4.1 , Strongly disagree	4.2 - 5.0	

The descriptive statistics results shown in Table 4.41 reveal that trainees disagree at 43.6 percent that there is career guidance department offering career advice, 38.1 percent of them agreed, 10.6 percent strongly agreed and those who strongly disagreed at 7.7 percent. Item mean rating 3.0032. Standard deviation 1.24621. Based on this results majority of trainees reported that there is no career guidance department offering career advice. The descriptive statistics results also indicate that respondents disagree at 40.1 percent that, the institution provides in-depth information on the realities of individual courses, 35.6 percent of them agreed, while those who strongly agreed at 21.2 percent and 3.2 percent strongly disagreed. Item mean rating 3.3141. Standard deviation 1.27959. Therefore, descriptive statistics results making a conclusion the institution provides in-depth information on the realities of individual courses.

The descriptive analysis results too shows that 41.0 percent of trainees disagree that trainee had prior knowledge on training courses offered by CVET institutions. Those strongly disagreed were represented at 25.0 percent, 22.1 percent representing those who agreed, 9.9 percent strongly agreed while 1.9 percent were not sure. Item mean rating 2.5090. Standard deviation 1.33945. Therefore, most of the informants indicated that the trainee had no prior knowledge on training courses CVETIs. The results indicate that respondents at 62.8 percent of informants agreed that the trainees are informed about career paths available, those who disagreed and strongly agreed were both represented at 14.7 percent, 6.4 percent strongly disagreed and 1.3 percent were not sure. Item mean rating 3.6474 Standard deviation 1.09840. This is an indication that majority of trainees had an opinion that, they are informed about career paths available which could influence their future career progression. The results indicate that informants at 81.1 percent agreed that inadequate career guidance has negatively influenced career progression hence low enrolment, 7.1 percent disagreed, 5.1 percent were not sure, 4.8 percent strongly agreed and those who strongly disagreed were represented at 1.9 percent. Item mean

rating 3.7981. Standard deviation 0.71789. This clearly implies that majority of trainees reported that inadequate career guidance services has negatively influenced career progression hence low enrolment in CVET institutions.

The descriptive statistics results also indicate that respondents disagree at 68.9 percent the instructors provide guidance on the importance of vocational education to enhance further training, 15.4 percent agreed, 8.0 percent of them were not sure, 5.4 percent strongly disagreed, while 2.2 percent strongly agreed. Item mean rating 2.4006. Standard deviation 0.89104. Therefore, the descriptive statistics results making a conclusion that most of the respondents feel that the instructors do not provide guidance on the importance of vocational education to enhance further training.

Table 4.42 Summary of informants' responses on availability of career guidance services

Statement	Managers			Instructors			Trainees		overall
	N	Mean	Std. deviation	N	Mean	Std. deviation	N	Mean deviation	Mean
i). the institution has career guidance department offering career guidance	21	2.5238	1.07792	87	2.3678	1.0795	312	3.0032 1.24621	2.6316
ii). Trainees are timely encouraged on their career choices	21	3.6190	1.02353	87	2.8161	1.12610	312	3.3141 1.27959	3.2497
iii). The trainees had prior knowledge on the training courses available in CVETIs	21	2.1429	1.06234	87	2.4828	1.27464	312	2.5090 1.33945	2.3782
iv). Trainees are guided on career paths for to enhance future career progression	21	3.0476	1.11697	87	3.1494	1.19600	312	3.6474 1.09840	3.2815
v).inadequate career guidance negatively influence career progression	21	3.5714	1.12122	87	3.5402	1.11860	312	3.7981 0.71789	3.6366
vi). The institution campaigns for vocational education through print and other social media	21	2.6667	1.15470	87	2.8621	1.14295	312	2.4006 0.89104	2.6431
Valid N (listwise) N=420	N=21			N=87			N=312		2.970

Table 4.42 provides a summary of managers', instructors' and trainees' responses to items presented to determine the influence of career guidance on access to CVET institutions. From the summary it appears that a majority of the vocational institutions had no functional career guidance department (mean=2.6316). However, a majority of the managers indicated that the institutions provides in-depth information on individual courses (mean=3.6190). It was also established that the trainees are informed about career paths for progressive training (mean= 3.2815). When asked whether the trainees had prior knowledge on the training courses offered by CVET institutions, the respondents overwhelmingly indicated that the trainees were not informed (mean. 2.3782).The researcher was interested to establish whether inadequate career guidance services could negatively influence career progression. This was based on assumption that career guidance on career progression could encourage them to enroll for artisan grade II and grade I which in turn increases the enrolment. Most of the respondents agreed that career guidance is essential for career progression whose long run effect is to boost the Vocational training institutions enrolment (mean= 3.6366). Based on the study findings, the failure to have functional career guidance department is an indication that trainees are not properly inducted through a welcome pack where they are given more information about their individual areas of specialization. This implies that the instructors and the managers have not played their role of continued induction as the trainees acclimatize to the new level of study. This could negatively affect the trainees' ambitions for further education and training which may lead to low enrolment. This findings concurred with a study by Watters (2009), on "making initial vocational education and training more attractive for prospective trainees". The study observed that, career departments have inadequate expertise to guide the trainees on career progression that makes it difficult to enroll for higher level of training in the institution or in other related institutions. Basically, inadequate career guidance in any institution of learning, limited information on career progression and labour market remuneration may lead to low drive in pursuing further

training which may lead to low rates of enrolment in TVET institutions and other institutions of education and training. Their response on whether the trainees had prior knowledge about the vocational training courses indicated that the trainees had inadequate information about the same. This implies that VET in the County has not gained a high social acceptance and the current enrolment in VET could be as a result of the last option after missing on other institutions of education and training.

Mumtaz, Abdul & Asma (2018), on their study on “the impact of career counselling and vocational guidance on employment in TVET sub-sector” citing (Kok & low, 2017), indicated that, for students to make informed career choice and training path-way require professional career guidance to enable them develop self-awareness in personal interest, skills and knowledge, their potential, understand their weakness and assess occupational opportunities (Mumtaz, Abdul, & Asma, 2018). This insight makes career guidance an important component to solve the education and training challenges that developing countries are facing today. During an interview with the managers, a manager had an opinion that the gradual career aspiration development during an individuals’ early days of development is shaped by the individual’s social environment where career decisions are based on role models. It’s at this point that the young population wishes to become a Lawyer, a Medical doctor, an Engineer or any other social ranking career.

It was reported that rarely the young population will aspire to become artisans or craftsmen as the society has attached less weight of the said trades as they all aspire to join universities for various Degree courses. Based on this insight, vocational training in Makueni County has not been given prominence at the lower levels of schooling where the learners are gradually prepared to join various VET institutions after completing their basic education. The findings in Table 4.42 revealed that the trainees’ response on whether the institution has a functional career guidance department concurred with the managers’ and instructors. It can be concluded that the vocational institutions in the County are not formally organized to disseminate this important information. On whether the institution provides in-depth information on individual courses, their response was in line with the instructors’ response.

The trainees being the recipients of such an important information confirmed that indeed they have limited information about the realities of their training course in terms job market and other course requirements. Another key concern was based on whether the trainees had prior knowledge about the courses that are offered by VET institutions. The majority indicated that, they had no such information. This implies that the trainees had not gradually prepared themselves to pursue vocational education and training as their life-time career. The trainees were found to be aware of the various training paths in their various areas of specialization as given by the majority of the respondents. Career guidance enable the young population and others to make a choice in wide range of available training opportunities and training courses, based on their distinctive abilities, interests and ability to both direct and in direct costs of training. This implies that “career guidance is indispensable within TVET, based on the evidence that enrolment to a vocational course indicates a deliberate career decision has been made (UNESCO, 2013)”.

CONCLUSION

In evaluating the contribution of career guidance on access to vocational education and training institutions, the quantitative descriptive results from the questionnaires showed that, career guidance has an influence on access to vocational education and training institutions. The study found that most of the sampled vocational institutions had no organized and functional career guidance departments. As a result, the instructors does not provide in-depth information on individual courses. Further, the instructors had not played their role of continued induction as the trainees acclimatize to their new level of training which could negatively affect the trainees’ ambition for further education and training leading to low enrolment. The study revealed that, vocational education and training has not gained a high social acceptance in the county. Inadequate career services implies that the trainees are denied the opportunity to explore the expectations surrounding the details of their career paths. The provision of in-depth information on the realities of a particular course could encourage the trainees to progressively enroll for higher levels of Vocational Education and Training which could improve their productivity and hence increase their chances of employment.

RECOMMENDATIONS OF THE STUDY

The main focus of this study was to improve CVET delivery system and increase the trainees’ enrolment. The findings of the study revealed that enrolment in County Vocational Education and Training institutions has remained low in Makueni County. Based on this findings the following recommendations have been made.

(1) The institutions should establish functional career guidance departments and provide in-depth information about individual course requirements and progressive training path ways available. (2) Career guidance on vocational education to be introduced at the lower level of basic education.

(3) The government should establish a strategic and sustainable campaign platforms for TVET targeting the parents, guardians and other members of the larger society who participate in the process of assisting the youth on making a choice for a training path way.

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